

D3.2. Documents for engaging the policy-makers, including a plan for standardization of PPB-based products of COST Action PurpleGain CA21146

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1. Executive summary

WG3 is focused on the relationships among academia, industry, and public entities related to the production and use of biomasses of purple phototrophic bacteria (PPB) and associated bioproducts. Some products examples from PPB are single-cell proteins, polyhydroxyalkanoates, carotenoids, or nutrient-rich biomass. The deliverable D3.1 showed the state of the art of PPB-based technologies currently used in different sectors across the biotechnology, food, and environmental industries, among others. An analysis of how similar and competing technologies are used will be made to establish benchmarks for PPB, as well as how the potential PPB-based products fit over the current policy practices in the EU and overseas, trying to fill the gap between direct engagement with policymakers.

2. Purpose

The target of this deliverable is to engage policymakers, including a plan for harmonization and standardization of PPB-based products, and includes technologies, products, applications, standardization, certification, labelling, and barriers. Raising awareness about PPB-based production possibilities, market niches (e.g., different than traditional markets of competing technologies and products) and related costs is one of key areas to observe.

3. Status and drive for PPB products and technologies in EU – Taxonomy

Figure 1 summarizes PPB-based biorefinery pathways for waste and wastewater valorization. Studies have shown that these systems can efficiently produce hydrogen, which can be used for clean energy applications, clean water, and biomass that is directed towards various sustainable end uses. Treated water can be re-used in different applications, including farming and aquaculture. PPB can efficiently capture nutrients from used streams, resulting in not only treating the water and wastes but also producing nutrient- and protein-rich biomasses that can be valorised for instance in agriculture or aquaculture. PPB biomass can also be the source of high-value bioproducts such as carotenoids, polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), and coenzyme Q10, which have applications in health, industry, and bioplastics. Furthermore, the biomass can be transformed into nutritious animal feed and fertilizers. PPB-based biorefineries can play a significant role in advancing circular economy goals in the waste and wastewater sectors by creating circular loops of nutrient and resource reuse.

Figure 1. Purple phototrophic bacteria for resource recovery: Challenges and opportunities. (Capson-Tojo, G., Batstone, D.J., Grassino, M., Vlaeminck, S.E., Puyol, D., Verstraete, W., Kleerebezem, R., Oehmen, A., Ghimire, A., Pikaar, I. and Lema, J.M., 2020 *Biotechnology advances*, 43, p.107567)

3.1 Technologies

Table 1 provides a snapshot of PPB technologies ranging from lab to demonstrative scale (TRL 3 to TRL 8), applied in fields like wastewater treatment, biotechnology and energy.

Table 1. PurpleGain results for current technology status

TECHNOLOGIES	State of the Art/ current state of development	Applications/ Market evaluation	Details/Additional Information (Location, scale etc.)
Anaerobic raceway ponds	Demonstrative scale (TRL 8)	Wastewater, waste streams	Linares WWTP, Jaen, Spain, 350 m ³ anaerobic raceway.
Anaerobic raceway pond	Demonstrative scale (TRL 8)	Wastewater, waste streams	Badajoz WWTP, Badajoz, Spain. 150 m ³
Anaerobic raceway pond	Demonstrative scale (TRL 7)	Wastewater, waste streams, bioplastics	Badajoz, Spain. 35 m ³ raceway
Anaerobic raceway pond	Pilot scale (TRL 6)	Wastewater, waste streams	Mostoles, Spain. 0.7 m ³
Raceway pond	Demonstrative scale (TRL 7)	Wastewater, waste streams, bioplastics	El Torno WWTP, Chiclana de la Frontera, Spain 19m ³ raceway

Flat-plate photobioreactor	Pilot scale (TRL 6)	Wastewater, waste streams	Brisbane, Australia, 0.9 m ³ (10 m) reactor
Flat-plate Photo-MBR	Lab scale (TRL 4)	Wastewater, waste streams	Brisbane, Australia, 2 L reactor
Gas-fed bubble-column photobioreactor	Lab scale (TRL 4)	Food, feed	Narbonne, France, 5 L reactor
Flat-plate Photo-MBR	Pilot scale (TRL 6)	Wastewater, waste streams	
Tubular photobioreactor	Pre-pilot scale (TRL 5)	Wastewater, biotechnology, food industry	Mostoles, Spain, 150 L
Chemostat photobioreactor	Lab scale (TRL 3)	Biotechnology, food, pharmacy, bioplastics, hydrogen industries	
Photo-bioelectrochemical reactor	Lab scale (TRL 4)	Energy, wastewater, food industry	Móstoles, Spain, 7 L

3.2 Products

Table 2 lists PPB-based biorefinery concepts including bioplastics, biofertilizers, biostimulants, proteins, and clean water, with development ranging from lab scale (TRL 3) to demonstrative scale (TRL 8), aimed at applications in packaging, agriculture, wasteland recovery, food and feed industries, and wastewater treatment.

Table 2. PurpleGain results for current product status

Source/ Feedstock	Technology	PRODUCTS	State of the Art/ current state of development	Applications	Details/ Additional Information (Location, scale etc.)
Wastewater, food waste	Raceway pond	Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA)	Demonstrative scale (TRL 7)	Packaging, materials, Wastewater treatment	El Torno WWTP, Chiclana de la Frontera, Spain
Wastewater	Flat-plate photobioreactor	Organic fertilizers	Pilot scale (TRL 6)	Agriculture	The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia
Wastewater	Anaerobic raceway pond	Organic fertilizers	Demonstrative scale (TRL 8)	Agriculture	Linares WWTP, Jaen, Spain
		Biostimulants	Lab scale (TRL 3)	Agriculture, wasteland recovery	

Wastewater, biogas	Flat-plate photobioreactor; gas-fed photobioreactor	Proteins	Pilot scale (TRL 6); lab scale (TRL 3)	Food & feed industries	The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia; INRAE, Narbonne, France
Wastewater	Anaerobic raceway pond; flat-plate photobioreactor	Clean water, organic fertilizers	Demonstrative scale (TRL 8)	Wastewater treatment	Linares WWTP, Jaen, Spain; Badajoz WWTP, Spain; The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia

Table 3 presents a summary of various products and services derived from different types of PPB systems, outlining the specific substrates used and the volume ranges for production, reported in the literature. It shows that a variety of products such as 5-ALA, carotenoids, coenzyme Q10, gold nanoparticles, lipids, and others are produced using batch or continuous processes in bioreactors like CSTR, PBR, and SBR. The substrates range from wastewater derivatives to various organic acids and sugars, with production volumes that have been investigated until now vary from as little as 0.020 up to 800 cubic meters.

Table 3. From Purple phototrophic bacteria for resource recovery: Challenges and opportunities

(Capson-Tojo, G., Batstone, D.J., Grassino, M., Vlaeminck, S.E., Puyol, D., Verstraete, W., Kleerebezem, R., Oehmen, A., Ghimire, A., Pikaar, I. and Lema, J.M., 2020. *Biotechnology advances*, 43, p.107567)

Product/Service	Reactor Type	Substrate	Volume (m ³)
5-ALA	Batch, CSTR	Food processing WW, AD effluent, Mixed VFAs + Different organics, Straw + Synthetic media	0.07-0.8
Carot	Batch	Citric acid + Corn syrup, Yeast extract, Malate, Glutamate, Domestic ww	0.015-0.5
Coenzyme Q10	CSTR, Fed-batch, Batch	Malic acid + casamino acid, Glucose, Acetate, Malate, Sucrose, Citrate, Fructose, Malate + tobacco hydrolysate, Malate + alfa hydrolysate, Malate + spinach hydrolysate	0.5-90
Gold nanoparticles	Batch	Pyruvate + HAuCl ₄	0.02
Lipids	Fed-batch, CSTR, PAnMBR	Malate, Lactate	1-1.07
Methane	Batch		
O-polysaccharide	Batch		

PHA	Raceways (Volume 19m3)	Wastewater/waste streams	0.14g PHA.L-1.d-1
PHB	Batch, Tubular PBR, SBR	Acetate, Butyrate, VFA mixture, Lactate, Pyruvate, Succinate, Glucose, DF effluent, Malate, Fumarate, Propionate, Gluconate, Glycerol, Citrate	0.02-5
Polyphosphate	Batch	Malate	
SCP	Tubular PBR, CSTR	Acetate, Other industrial ww	4 - 53
WWT	Batch, CSTR, PAnMBR, SBR, Open-PB (Rs, Open-PAnMBR, PAnMBR, Fed-batch attached, MSBR, Overflow PBR, Suspended bed reactor, PRBC	Acetate, Propionate, Butyrate, VFA mixture, Fish industry, industrial, Food processing, Meat processing, Domestic, Dairy, Poultry, Piggery WWs, AD digestate, Glucose (synthetic WW), Malate, Lactate, Succinate, Oxaloacetate, synthetic WW, Amylose, Valerate, Caproate, polluted lake, Ethanol, Lactic acid, Citric acid WW	0.05 - 800
H ₂	Baffled-Continuous Reactor, Batch annular PBR, Column PBR, CSTR, Fed-batch Panel PBR, Microchannel PBR, Panel PBR, SBR, Semi-continuous, Tubular PBR,	Butyrate, VFA mixture, Acetate + lactate, Succinate + acetate, Propionate, Succinate, Ethanol, Glucose, Corn stalk pith hydrolysate, SSFF effluent, Glycerol, Sucrose, Pyruvate, Valerate, Caproate, Isovalerate, Xylose, Arabinose, Cellobiose, Maltose, Sugar processing WW	0.0041-8000 L

4. General barriers for PPB products and technologies

Table 4 provides a comprehensive overview of various EU regulations relevant to the production and market placement of bioproducts, bioplastics, biofertilizers, biostimulants and proteins, as well as the technologies associated with wastewater treatment. It also outlines regulatory barriers each category faces, along with economic, social, and technological challenges. The regulations span from emissions reduction to organic labelling and novel foods, indicates a complex legislative landscape. Barriers highlighted include the lack of specific provisions for biobased products, high certification costs, and resource-intensive authorization processes. Economic and social challenges include limited market awareness and the need to build trust with consumers. Technological challenges refer to issues such as high production and harvesting costs besides the poor efficiencies. The

analysis underscores the multifaceted upscaling challenges that technology developers can face in navigating the regulatory environment and market acceptance.

Table 4. PurpleGain results for barriers products and technologies

PRODUCTS	Regulation	Regulatory Barriers	Other (Economic, social, technological)
General	<p>2016/2284 - on the reduction of national emissions of certain atmospheric pollutants</p> <p>2009/28/EC Renewable Energy Directive - on indirect land use changes (ILUC)</p> <p>Regulation No 1907/2006 on the Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), establishing a European Chemicals Agency, amending certain Directive</p> <p>2009/125/EC Eco-design Directive - on establishing a framework for the setting of eco-design requirements for energy-related products</p>	<p>Existing regulatory frameworks may lack specific provisions or incentives to encourage the uptake of PPB and other biobased products, making it challenging for businesses to invest in their development and commercialization.</p> <p>As biobased products from purple bacteria can involve novel chemical compositions, the existing regulatory guidelines may not fully account for their unique characteristics.</p> <p>Eco-design Directive: specific provisions not well-tailored to address the attributes and potential of biobased products from purple bacteria.</p>	<p>Limited awareness and recognition of biobased products from purple bacteria as viable alternatives for reducing atmospheric pollutants.</p> <p>Still uncertainties and high costs regarding the appropriate categorization, testing requirements, and authorization procedures, certification of novel biobased products hinder their smooth integration into the market.</p>

Bioplastics	Waste Framework Directive (revision) Packaging and Packaging Waste (revision)	<p>Still unclear the preferable end-of-life treatment – a small market inhibits centralized recycling.</p> <p>Lack of legislative framework for bio-based plastics.</p> <p>There are multiple overlapping schemes for the certification of bioproducts.</p> <p>Certification is expensive, time-consuming and requires significant expertise.</p>	
Fertilizers	Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 – laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products	<p>Regulatory and policy constraints, regulatory framework is complex and varies, obtaining necessary permits is resource intensive.</p> <p>Ensuring consistent quality and performance can be challenging – robust quality control measures are needed. Building trust and acceptance with end-users and consumers.</p>	
Organic fertilizers	Commission Regulation (EC) No 889/2008 of 5 September 2008 laying down detailed rules for the implementation of Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007 on organic production and labelling of organic products with regard to organic production, labelling and control	Labelling is difficult and time-consuming.	

	Fertilizers Regulation (EU) 2019/1009		
Biostimulants	<u>REACH Regulation (EC 1907/2006)</u>	Regulation and guidelines for production is missing.	
Proteins	Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 on Animal By-products Regulation (EU) No 2015/2283 on Novel Foods	Quality and safety concerns. Lack of accepted PPB species on EFSA list.	
Wastewater treatment (WWT)	Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse (Text with EEA relevance)	Water reuse awareness raising is not fulfilled effectively.	Poor biomass settleability, low nutrients removal capacity. Water reuse is contradictory.
TECHNOLOGIES	Regulation		
Open Pond	Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) (<u>Council Directive 91/271/EEC</u>)		
Anaerobic raceway pond			Already developed (TRL 8)
Flat-plate Photo-MBR			High land use, poor volume/surface ratio
Tubular photobioreactor			Lack of efficient materials for natural illumination, poor biomass harvesting
Chemostat photobioreactor			High illumination costs, poor biomass harvesting
Photo-bioelectrochemical reactor			Poor volume/surface ratio, high materials costs

5. Standardization, Certification, and Labelling of PPB products

5.1 Existing standards, labels in different sectors

Tables 5 and 6 detail the existing industry standards and certifications for potential PPB-based bioproducts, including biobased content for bioplastics, characterization guidelines for biofertilizers, organic certifications for biostimulants, and food safety management for proteins, reflecting the regulatory and certification landscape across various applications.

Table 5. PurpleGain analysis of existing certifications and labels for different PPB based bio-products

PRODUCTS	Existing Standards	Existing labels and certifications	PPB Applications
Bioplastics	CEN/TR 15932 Plastics– Recommendation for characterisation of biopolymers & plastics	<p>Labels related to compostability, Biodegradation</p> <p>Test methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •DIN EN 13432 (Europe) •T51 –800 (France) •ASTM D 5338 (plastics, aerobic biodegradation) •ISO 16929 (plastics disintegration) <p>Relevant bodies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Vincotte, Belgium •DIN CERTCO, Germany •Jätelaitosyhdistys, Finland •ADEME, France <p>Labels related to biobased content (i.e. biobased carbon content)</p>	Currently no known PHA commercialized from PPB production
Biofertilizers	ISO 16187:2012 provides guidelines for characterizing mineral fertilizers and soil conditioners	<p>OMRI Listed (Organic Materials Review Institute): Certification indicating that a product is suitable for use in certified organic production, handling, and processing.</p> <p>ECOCERT: An organic certification organization that also certifies natural</p>	Applications up to demonstrative scale (TRL 7) in the H2020.JTI.BBI DEEP PURPLE project.

		and organic fertilizers, which can include biostimulants.	
Biostimulants	The European Biostimulants Industry Council (EBIC) offers guidelines and definitions for different types of biostimulants	ECOCERT: An organic certification organization that also certifies natural and organic fertilizers, which can include biostimulants	
Proteins	ISO 22000 sets out the requirements for a food safety management system and can be applied to the production of biotechnological proteins	FSSC 22000: A food safety certification scheme that covers the manufacturing process of animal proteins, including those produced via biotechnology.	

Table 6. PurpleGain analysis of existing standards applicable to various categories of PPB

PRODUCTS	Existing Standards	Description
Other standards	CEN/TR 16721:2014	Bio-based products - Overview of methods to determine the biobased content.
	EN 16785-1:2015	Bio-based products - Bio-based content - Part 1: Determination of the bio-based content using the radiocarbon analysis and elemental analysis.
	EN 16640:2017 & EN 16640:2017/AC:2017	Bio-based products - Bio-based carbon content - Determination of the bio-based carbon content using the radiocarbon method.
	NF U 52-001 Biodegradable materials–Mulching products–Req. & test methods	Requirements and test methods for biodegradable mulching materials, which are commonly made from organic, renewable resources.
	EN 16751 Bio-based products–Sustainability criteria	Establishes sustainability criteria for assessing the environmental and social impacts of products derived from renewable biological resources.
	EN 16760 Bio-based products–Life Cycle Assessment	Provides guidelines for conducting life cycle assessments (LCA) to evaluate the environmental impacts of products derived from renewable biological resources.

	CEN/TR 16957 Bio-based products–Guidelines for LCI for the EoL phase	Linked with biobased products as it offers guidelines for conducting Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) assessments specifically focused on the End-of-Life (EoL) phase of products derived from renewable biological resources.
	ASTM E 3066a Standard Practice for Evaluating Relative Sustainability Involving Energy or Chemicals from Biomass	Outlines a practice for assessing the relative sustainability of products involving energy or chemicals derived from biomass, thereby evaluating their environmental impact and contribution to sustainability.
	EN 16575 Bio-based products - Vocabulary	Terminology.
	EN 16935 Bio-based products – Requirements for Business to Consumer communication and Claim	Sets requirements for effective communication and claims made by businesses to consumers regarding the bio-based content and environmental attributes of products.

6. Identifying opportunities – PURPLE GAIN action plan

Gaps of existing standards/certifications:

- Still unclear how to evaluate the downstream assessment aspects (such as manufacturing and beyond) until the product reaches its end-of-life stage
- Approaches need to be developed considering the risks of biobased products from PPB
- Standardization of requirements defining sustainable biomass is missing and existing schemes are not harmonized. Sustainability criteria are mandatory for biofuels, but this should be extended to other biobased products
- Regulations are currently missing to promote the certification of new value chains
- All existing schemes are voluntary/ there are no legal requirements validating that biobased products are sustainable
- Not well-established criteria to assess the environmental and sustainability aspects unique to PPB value chains
- Landscape of certifications and labels is fragmented, and it can be challenging for consumers and businesses to navigate and compare the various claims and standards
- Limited awareness of citizens and businesses limiting uptake and acceptance of existing certifications
- Existing certifications focus on specific products (i.e. bioplastic), certifications for other biobased products are still underdeveloped
- Certifications are costly and require significant time and resources, which is challenging for small-medium SMEs

7. Concluding remarks

It is evident that PPB-based biorefineries offer a promising pathway for advancing circular economy goals in waste and wastewater sectors. However, the scaling up and commercialization of these technologies are hindered by technological, regulatory, social, and economic barriers. The regulatory framework needs to be streamlined to better accommodate the unique characteristics of PPB-based products, reduce certification costs, and promote market awareness. Many obstacles are persisting related to water-reuse, labelling of organic products etc, which need to be solved in due time.

Incentives for innovation in this field are mandatory to overcome the current challenges of integrating PPB technologies into existing markets and to leverage their potential for sustainable development.